

Review

Advancement in non-destructive methodologies for the determination of meat fraud

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Abstract: Food fraud is a new term worldwide and can involve many different stages of the production process. It affects safety, quality, consumer acceptance, and profitability. Food fraud assessment methods need to be very precise and reliable. Most animal-origin foods, including milk, dairy products, meat and meat products, eggs, fish, and fisheries goods, are vulnerable to food fraud. Identifying any adulteration in them is essential to stop unfair competition and protect consumer rights. Due to financial benefits, meat and meat products are vulnerable to various forms of adulteration. The meat business is transitioning from laborious and time-consuming analytical procedures to quick, non-invasive, non-destructive, repeatable, and trustworthy analytical technologies. This reviews precision analytical methods like near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy and machine learning algorithms, linear regression, principal component analysis, etc., for detecting food fraud in meat and meat products.

Keywords: food fraud; nondestructive methods; NIR spectroscopy; machine learning algorithm; linear regression

1. Introduction

Food fraud occurs globally and can encompass all aspects of food production. This issue transcends mere financial concerns; it also impacts consumer safety, quality, and equity. As the methods employed for deception become increasingly sophisticated, there is a pressing need for enhanced techniques to ascertain whether food has been adulterated. These procedures must be precise and dependable [1]. Foods of animal origin, such as milk, dairy products, meat and meat products, eggs, fish, and seafood, are frequently contaminated. Detecting any adulteration is crucial to prevent unfair competition and safeguard consumer rights [2]. Nonetheless, frequently, such instances of food fraud are associated with financial gains achieved by adulteration intended to lower production costs or extend shelf life [3]. A concerning matter is that meat and meat products are susceptible to multiple forms of adulteration [4]. Deliberate replacements of lower-quality species or materials for premium raw components, the inclusion of undeclared proteins from various sources, or the sale of frozen-thawed meat as fresh are common instances [5]. The appeal is clear, as fresh meat holds greater value than frozen meat. The freezing process leads to the formation of ice crystals, which physically damage microstructures. This procedure is reiterated throughout the freezing and thawing stages, alongside continuous recrystallization [6]. This investigation observed that frozen-thawed chicken meat does not possess the qualitative features typical of fresh-chilled meat.

The meat industry is expected to gradually shift from labor-intensive and time-consuming analytical methods to rapid, non-invasive, non-destructive, repeatable, and reliable advanced analytical technologies [5,7–10]. The techniques for assessing meat samples for authenticity should preferably be non-destructive, applicable on-site or in-line at an abattoir or factory, and exhibit a high level of accuracy and reproducibility.

2. NIR spectroscopy

2.1. Basics of NIR spectroscopy

An analytical technique that is quick, non-invasive, chemical-free, non-destructive, and ecologically benign is near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy. A spectroscopic technique called near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) uses the electromagnetic spectrum's near-infrared (from 780 nm to 2500 nm) region. It is a laboratory method that examines the diffuse reflectance radiation to determine the chemical makeup of a substance. The basic principles and application of NIRS in meat quality assessment have been illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Basic principle and uses of NIR in meat quality assessment.

There are three categories of infrared radiation: far-infrared (FIR), mid-infrared (MIR), and near-infrared (NIR). These regions are most frequently employed in food analysis because organic compounds are absorbed in the NIR and MIR areas. The most essential characteristics of the NIR spectroscopic region are reflected in the analytical methods that arise from using it. These include being fast (one minute or less per sample), low cost, non-destructive, non-invasive, and suitable for in-line use. They

also have a nearly universal application (any molecule containing C-H, N-H, S-H, or O-H bonds) with minimal requirements for sample preparation [11].

The length of the transmission through a sample is influenced by the particles' size, shape, and arrangement and the spaces between them, which in turn affects reflectance [12]. Near-infrared spectra have mixtures of vibrational bands and faint overtones, making them challenging to analyze directly. Therefore, multivariate calibration is necessary to perform a quantitative study of the sample elements using NIRS. NIR spectroscopy is becoming a potent tool for the quantitative and qualitative analysis of food components when used in conjunction with chemometrics techniques [13]. Before and after interacting with the sample, the light intensity as a function of wavelength is measured, and the diffuse reflectance, a mix of absorption and scattering caused by the sample is computed. The sample absorbs light in different proportions at frequencies that match the overtones and combinations of vibrational frequencies of specific bond vibrations in the sample. The details of the NIR classification model have been illustrated in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Overview of NIR spectroscopy classification model.

2.2. Application of NIR spectroscopy classification and adulteration detection

The method has been used for the quantitative analysis of the main components of meat and meat products, including moisture, fat, and protein [14], and also for discrimination between frozen and unfrozen beef [15]. By fusing cutting-edge classification algorithms with portable, handheld near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, Parastar et al. [16] created a potent technique for determining the authenticity of chicken meat. The research presented demonstrates that using NIR spectra, it is feasible to distinguish between fresh and thawed meat and to accurately categorize chicken fillets depending on the growing circumstances of the chickens. With a classification accuracy of $> 95\%$, the random subspace discriminant ensemble (RSDE) method consistently beat other popular classification techniques, including support

vector machines (SVM), artificial neural networks (ANN), and partial least squares-discriminant analysis (PLS-DA).

In order to research food freshness, Eui et al. [17] used a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based machine learning method to assess the spectrum response from a portable visible/near-infrared (VIS/NIR) spectrometer. For thirty hours every minute, spectral response data from tuna, salmon, and beef incubated at 25 °C were obtained. Based on time and pH, the data were then divided into three states: fresh, likely rotting, and ruined.

To assess the freshness of the experimental items, a CNN-based machine-learning method was developed using the gathered spectral data. Moreover, variance caused by using several devices in a real-world scenario may be lessened by using a CNN-based machine learning approach with a shift-invariant feature. With the use of spectral data, a machine learning model was able to accurately estimate the freshness of salmon (85%), tuna (88%), and beef (92%). Nolasco et al. [18] employed ML algorithms in conjunction with portable NIR equipment to categorize chicken parts, specifically the drumsticks, thighs, and breasts. The chemical composition (protein, fat, moisture, and ash) and physical characteristics (pH and L*, a*, and b* color features) were ascertained for every sample. Principal component analysis was employed as a screening method after spectral data in the 900–1700 nm region was obtained using a portable NIR spectrophotometer. Random forest and support vector machine methods were contrasted to categorize chicken flesh. Findings demonstrated that breast samples from thighs and drumsticks could be distinguished with 98.8% accuracy. The outcomes demonstrated the possibility of differentiating chicken parts in the processing business by combining an ML technique with a portable NIR spectrophotometer.

Using the linear least mean squares (LMS) classifier, Kamruzzaman et al. [19] discovered that it provided the most significant classification accuracy, reaching 96.67%. Additionally, they discovered that the categorization problem became more difficult with adding a second muscle. Findings of Sanz et al. [20] distinguished between lamb muscles using hyperspectral imaging in the 380–1028 nm wavelength range by including an extra muscle type and employing more samples. Their research employed four distinct muscle types—LD, ST, PM, and semimembranosus (SM)—from thirty different breed animals. Furthermore, Alomar et al. [21], using NIR spectroscopy in the 400–2500 nm wavelength range, separated distinct forms of bovine muscle and predicted many chemical fractions from two breeds and three muscles (LD, ST, and supraspinatus (SS)). The findings revealed that the three muscle types produced classification accuracy of 97.8% (LD), 97.7% (SS), and 89.5% (ST), while the two breeds were accurately categorized with 78.8% accuracy.

Al-Sarayreh et al. [22] detected adulterated red meat using deep spectral-spatial features in hyperspectral pictures. A collection of line-scanning photos of muscles from lamb, cattle, or pig was made while considering the meat's condition (fresh, frozen, thawed, and sample packed and unpacked using a clear bag). Meat muscles were classified as belonging to either the class of lamb or the class of beef or pig in order to simulate the adulteration problem. According to the results, regardless of the condition of the items, the CNN model performs the best, with an overall classification

accuracy of 94.4%. Every class at every stage receives a high F1 score from the CNN model. The resultant CNN model is believed to be straightforward and mostly independent of the meat's state. They demonstrated the effectiveness of hyperspectral imaging systems as quick, accurate, and non-destructive methods for spotting adulteration in red meat products.

According to Sanchez et al. [23], research on classifying beef freshness using deep spectral networks was developed. The deep learning-based method was able to classify the freshness of beef by examining myoglobin data and reflectance spectra across different freshness stages. Following 17 days of reflectance spectrum measurements on 78 beef samples, the datasets were classified into three freshness classes based on the samples' pH values.

Myoglobin data revealed statistically significant variations based on freshness; as a result, it was used as an essential categorization criterion. The model performed better when the myoglobin data and the reflectance spectra were integrated. The single-spectra model's accuracy was 83.6%, while the suggested model's increased to 91.9%.

Additionally, a high value of 0.958 was observed for the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve. This work is a foundation for further research into the myoglobin data related to meat freshness. Detection of red-meat adulteration by deep spectral-spatial features in hyperspectral images. Machine learning techniques have been used to evaluate lamb meat. Previous research has used hyper-spectral imaging or objective and sensory measurements to forecast how tender lamb meat will be [24].

Additionally, the issue of utilizing artificial neural networks and ultrasound pictures to estimate the intramuscular fat content of lamb muscle has been addressed [25]. Other studies have been carried out to predict lamb meat adulteration using multiple linear regression [25].

3. Principal component analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a widely recognized statistical technique used for dimensionality reduction, which generates new variables (principal components) by forming linear combinations of the original variables in an unsupervised manner. A small number of principal components can preserve the same information as numerous original variables and account for most of the data's variability [26]. Spectra of fresh and frozen mutton were scanned and investigated to find typical patterns, differences, or similarities in signal characteristics before setting up the calibration model. Kamruzzaman et al. [19] used NIR hyperspectral imaging to discriminate lamb muscles (semitendinosus (ST), longissimus dorsi (LD), and psoas major (PM)) in a wavelength range of 900–1700 nm. They used principal component analysis (PCA) for wavelength reduction and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) [27] to build classification models.

4. Machine learning

4.1. Machine learning software

Python's interactive features and robust libraries have made it a popular high-level programming language for scientific computing applications. The scikit-learn open-source machine learning toolbox has many efficient machine learning methods. These techniques cover many essential machine-learning issues, such as feature selection, supervised and unsupervised learning, data transformation, and model assessment [28].

With functions for data representation, data preprocessing, numerical operations, linear algebra, random number generation, and evaluation metrics, NumPy is a crucial library for Python machine learning. It is an essential tool for machine learning applications because of its practical mathematical functions and array operations. With features for data visualization, model assessment, hyperparameter tweaking, debugging, and reporting, Matplotlib is a crucial toolkit for machine learning data visualization. Seaborn and Matplotlib are used to create confusion matrices and spectral data line plots. TensorFlow is an open-source library designed for numerical computing and advanced machine learning. Pandas is a library that supports data manipulation in machine learning, offering tools for data cleaning, merging, joining, time series analysis, and feature engineering [29].

4.2. Machine learning classification models

To make an informed choice, machine learning (ML) uses a variety of algorithms to interpret data and then apply what it learns [30]. Machine learning needs little human intervention after deployment since it uses data to feed an algorithm (**Figure 3**) that can comprehend the link between input and output [31]. Based on the volume of data they get, machine learning algorithms can generate their predictions [32]. ML models may be divided into four main groups according to their input data type. Supervised, semi-supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning are those four categories. One kind of machine learning is supervised learning, which uses labeled examples or datasets to train a model [33]. The labeled dataset consists of labels—a term for the output targets that correlate to the input attributes. In the training phase, the machine learning algorithm analyzes the labeled data by analyzing patterns or correlations between the input characteristics and the related output targets. The algorithm's accuracy is assessed on a fresh dataset, known as the testing dataset, once it has been trained on the labeled dataset. The input characteristics in the testing dataset do not have associated labels, making it an unlabeled dataset. The accuracy of the model's output label predictions for the testing dataset is determined by contrasting the model's predictions with the actual labels in the dataset. The model can be applied in the actual world if its accuracy is deemed enough. On the other hand, the model may be adjusted to perform better if its accuracy is low. To increase the model's accuracy on the testing dataset, fine-tuning may entail changing the features, tweaking the hyperparameters, or utilizing an alternative method.

Figure 3. Classification of the most common machine learning algorithms.

4.2.1. Linear discriminant analysis

In machine learning, supervised learning algorithms like linear discriminant analysis (LDA) are used for classification tasks. LDA identifies the linear combination of features that most effectively separates the classes in a dataset. LDA projects the data onto a space with fewer dimensions to enhance the distinction between classes. It achieves this by identifying a set of linear discriminants that maximize the ratio of between-class variance to within-class variance. It identifies the directions in the feature space that most efficiently differentiate between various data classes. Linear discriminant analysis, as indicated by its nomenclature, is a linear model utilized for classification and dimensionality reduction. Predominantly employed for feature extraction in pattern classification issues [34]. LDA transforms data from a D -dimensional feature space to a D' -dimensional space (where $D > D'$) to optimize inter-class variance and minimize intra-class variation. Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) is a multi-class classification technique. It applies a p -dimensional multivariate normal distribution to the observations of each class. While the densities have distinct estimated means, they are constrained to share the same covariance structure [35].

4.2.2. Logistic regression

Another technique that machine learning has adapted from statistics is logistic regression. The goal of the supervised machine learning technique known as logistic regression is to estimate the likelihood that an instance belongs to a particular class in classification problems [36].

4.2.3. Random forest classifier

Breiman [37] created the random forest (RF) method. Through analyzing several meat quality variables and their interconnections, Random Forest (RF) can identify the primary determinants of meat quality [38]. The RF algorithm has been utilized in this study to take advantage of this benefit. RF, also known as classification and regression trees (CART) [39], implements tree-based methods. Using this method, a

dataset is divided into subsets, or nodes, that make up a binary tree structure [40], each subsequent subset being more homogeneous than the original set in terms of the classifications. The root node, which houses all samples, is split into two halves at the start of the splitting process. Until terminal nodes are reached, this process is repeated for every child node and the descending nodes that result from it. When all of the samples in a node are thought to be sufficiently homogeneous—when they all belong to the same class—the node is said to be a terminal node [40]. CART is a popular classification algorithm [41] that has been used in food analysis and metabolomics. The RF technique employs a set of many classification trees for classification, each constructed from a distinct obtained segment of the data [37,42]. With bootstrapping, a sample may be taken from the set with replacement, and an RF classification tree is grown to the most significant extent for each sample. Iterating through this procedure yields distinct trees for every sample, culminating in an ensemble of trees. The classification of each tree is utilized to get the ensemble's average, which is subsequently used to determine the ensemble's classification [37,43]. RF is a relatively new statistical technique but is steadily gaining application in chemometrics [44–46].

4.2.4. Support vector machine

A family of supervised learning algorithms used for regression, outlier identification, and classification are called support vector machines (SVMs). SVMs have the advantage of working well in high-dimensional spaces and continuing to function effectively when there are more dimensions than samples. Vapnik and Cortes [47] created the binary classification support vector machine (SVM). An SVM is, therefore, coupled with a feature selection process based on sensitivity analysis to measure the softness of lamb meat [48]. Proposals have been put up to tackle the classification of lamb muscle types via machine learning techniques, including support vector machines, logistic regression, artificial neural networks, and linear discriminant analysis [19,20,49]. For data mining, a wide range of statistical categorization methods are available [41,43], including support vector machines (SVM), random forests (RF), and recursive partitioning (RP). The SVM's goal in classification is to create an ideal hyperplane that divides two distinct groups [43]. SVM is becoming a crucial instrument for chemometric data mining [41,50,51].

4.2.5. K-Nearest neighbors

KNN, in its most basic form, is based on estimating the class of the vector that the value to be estimated's independent variables form. The densest nearest neighbors' class information serves as the basis for this. The KNN algorithm, known as *K*-Nearest Neighbors, forecasts two primary variables. Based on an Euclidean distance calculation function, the distance value represents the estimated distance between a point and other points. The number of closest neighbors that the computation will be performed across determines the *K* value, or neighborhood number, which directly impacts the outcome. The likelihood of the model being overfit is relatively high if $K = 1$. If it is significantly higher, the model yields pretty broad conclusions. As a result, determining the ideal *K* value is an important step [52].

4.2.6. Confusion matrix

The target model's qualitative performance can be represented by the confusion matrix [52]. Three crucial indications are shown in the confusion matrix to display the classified information of the qualitative model: accuracy, precision, and sensitivity (also known as recall) [53]. This table allows one to examine the present state of the data collection and the number of accurate and inaccurate classification model predictions. Each class, regardless of size, has four values in the confusion matrix: False negative (FN), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and true positive (TP) [54]. The real negatives are $TN + FP$, and the real positives are $TP + FN$. It is possible to compute the performance of classification models using these data. More accurate classification may be achieved by adjusting the hyperparameters of the models in precision classification issues by attentively reviewing the confusion matrix data. The number of classes in the classification issue determines the size of the confusion matrices [55].

5. Conclusions

The meat industry is intricate and evolving, requiring cost-effective and eco-friendly methods that guarantee product quality and authenticity. Non-destructive methods can deliver a swift, uniform, and impartial evaluation of the samples being examined. When combined with suitable multivariate data or image analysis methods, they may serve as useful instruments for detecting adulterants and authenticating processed meat products. The evaluated spectroscopic and imaging techniques possess the capability for automation, hence obviating laborious and time-intensive conventional approaches. Significant constraints hindering the practical application of these non-destructive approaches encompass expensive equipment, the production of extensive data sets, protracted image processing protocols, and interpretation challenges. Expertise in scientific knowledge is essential for picking an effective and pragmatic classification method, as no technique is universally optimal; this may be a formidable challenge. Emerging advancements in meat fraud detection are focused on creating high-performance, cost-effective, and non-destructive technologies. Integrating outcomes from various non-destructive techniques, such as an imaging method alongside a non-imaging method, may yield a more comprehensive characterization of the sample being examined. The minimization of image size and enhancement of processing speed are critical factors for the use of these approaches in real-time applications. This evaluation mostly concentrated on adulteration; however, the technologies can also be employed for detecting chemical composition, nutritional profile, and microbiological contamination.

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